

N3C Query Report:

Paxlovid

Abstract

The overall goals of this query are to 1) characterize the growth in patients receiving Paxlovid over time and 2) examine Paxlovid use by patient characteristics, including by acute SARS CoV-2 infection profile and healthcare utilization. Patients with a COVID index date or a visit date between 12/1/2021 (7 days before EUA) and 5/30/2022 are included in the results. Based on the limited data currently available, we provide counts of patients who received paxlovid by site and characteristics of patients who received paxlovid at two time points (12/1/2021-3/31/22 and 4/1/22-5/30/22). In Q4, this will be expanded to include additional concepts (PASC, PASC sub-phenotypes, and re-infection).

Methods

Inclusion Criteria

- **Age:** any age
- **COVID-19 Positive:** via a qualifying index event between 12/1/2021 – 5/30/2022
 - Definition 1. Positive SARS-CoV-2 PCR test (no antibody tests)
 - Definition 2. Diagnosis of COVID-19 via 1 inpatient or 2 outpatient instances of ICD-10 code U07.1
- **COVID-19 Negative:** via a qualifying visit between 12/1/2021-5/30/2022
 - no indication of COVID-19
- **Paxlovid:** exposure to paxlovid as defined by the presence of a prescription for nirmatrelvir and ritonavir between 12/1/2021-5/30/2022 as defined below

Data used are from release version 82 of the N3C data enclave, released on June 23, 2022. Site-level quality filters were applied prior to analysis in order to remove 9 of the 74 data partners with significant and systematic missingness according to the following criteria: sites (1) should not shift dates by more than 30 days, (2) should have serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results for at least 25% of hospitalizations, and (3) should not have >10% of their hospitalizations where the COVID-19 index date is more than 200 days after the visit start date.

Definitions

Index event

The earliest instance of COVID-19 positivity between 12/1/2021 – 5/30/2022. This allows COVID index up to seven days before EUA of Paxlovid.

Paxlovid

A concept set was developed for nirmatrelvir and ritonavir. Concept sets contain concepts for the individual ingredient, as well as concepts for the combination of nirmatrelvir and ritonavir (Paxlovid pack). A patient who has a concept for nirmatrelvir and ritonavir on the same day is considered to be taking Paxlovid. Any course of Paxlovid was considered a prescription, whether prescribed, administered, or dispensed at a facility.

Results

Figure 1. Inclusion Criteria and Cohort Description

Observations: Above in Figure 1, we show an accounting of our inclusion criteria and cohort description. For the site-level analyses, we include close to 6 million patients with about 25% (~1.5 m) of those patients meeting definition one or two for COVID positivity. We exclude 1.8 m patients that had COVID index date outside of our study period (12/1/2021-5/30/2022); of those excluded, 1,077 received paxlovid. We describe the demographics, covid severity and paxlovid receipt for the patients who received paxlovid (15,291 COVID positive and 1,421 with no indication of COVID) during our study period below under each figure and table.

Figure 2. Paxlovid prescriptions given

Observations: We calculated the number of Paxlovid prescriptions given per week during the study period beginning from 12/1/2021. The Paxlovid prescriptions rose to 3,137 the week of May 23, 2022 before steeply declining to 183 prescriptions during the week of May 30, 2022.

Figure 3. All Medication Prescriptions given

Observations: All medication prescriptions were graphed per week during the study period beginning 12/1/2021. We observed a similar trend in decline of all medication prescriptions at the end of May. 2,872 “all medication” prescriptions were given the week of May 23, 2022 and declined to 252 prescriptions during the week of May 30, 2022. This is likely a reflection of data partners delay in submitting end of May data.

Table 1. Paxlovid use by Healthcare facilities (sorted by paxlovid prescriptions)

Facility UID	All Patient #	Paxlovid Prescriptions	COVID Patients	COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid	Non-COVID Patients	Non-COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid
All	6076060	16712	1550264 (25.5%)	15291 (1.0%)	4525796 (74.5%)	1421 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	366826	3543	64073 (17.5%)	3486 (5.4%)	302753 (82.5%)	57 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	205703	2527	38285 (18.6%)	2275 (5.9%)	167418 (81.4%)	252 (0.2%)
*** Masked ***	371291	2242	78684 (21.2%)	2169 (2.8%)	292607 (78.8%)	73 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	302751	1240	68115 (22.5%)	993 (1.5%)	234636 (77.5%)	247 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	92234	976	7952 (8.6%)	966 (12.1%)	84282 (91.4%)	<20
*** Masked ***	64674	948	15012 (23.2%)	877 (5.8%)	49662 (76.8%)	71 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	107792	817	18776 (17.4%)	563 (3.0%)	89016 (82.6%)	254 (0.3%)
*** Masked ***	167159	780	29246 (17.5%)	769 (2.6%)	137913 (82.5%)	<20
*** Masked ***	104078	767	16516 (15.9%)	766 (4.6%)	87562 (84.1%)	<20
*** Masked ***	116727	698	17673 (15.1%)	572 (3.2%)	99054 (84.9%)	126 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	158930	591	27560 (17.3%)	479 (1.7%)	131370 (82.7%)	112 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	42165	447	8993 (21.3%)	386 (4.3%)	33172 (78.7%)	61 (0.2%)
*** Masked ***	50714	300	10253 (20.2%)	257 (2.5%)	40461 (79.8%)	43 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	52583	285	10472 (19.9%)	249 (2.4%)	42111 (80.1%)	36 (0.1%)
*** Masked ***	87660	235	14245 (16.3%)	211 (1.5%)	73415 (83.7%)	24 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	163017	81	27236 (16.7%)	66 (0.2%)	135781 (83.3%)	<20

Facility UID	All Patient #	Paxlovid Prescriptions	COVID Patients	COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid	Non-COVID Patients	Non-COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid
*** Masked ***	19113	76	3407 (17.8%)	72 (2.1%)	15706 (82.2%)	<20
*** Masked ***	48440	57	6976 (14.4%)	43 (0.6%)	41464 (85.6%)	<20
*** Masked ***	34241	49	12528 (36.6%)	49 (0.4%)	21713 (63.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	90277	30	19829 (22.0%)	27 (0.1%)	70448 (78.0%)	<20
*** Masked ***	2344	<20	268 (11.4%)	<20	2076 (88.6%)	<20
*** Masked ***	38686	<20	6664 (17.2%)	<20	32022 (82.8%)	<20
*** Masked ***	113926	<20	13941 (12.2%)	<20	99985 (87.8%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	44172	0	8277 (18.7%)	0 (0.0%)	35895 (81.3%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	1146	0	32 (2.8%)	0 (0.0%)	1114 (97.2%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	80846	0	12795 (15.8%)	0 (0.0%)	68051 (84.2%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	132654	0	24384 (18.4%)	0 (0.0%)	108270 (81.6%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	72220	0	12619 (17.5%)	0 (0.0%)	59601 (82.5%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	72334	0	12764 (17.6%)	0 (0.0%)	59570 (82.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	95289	0	15865 (16.6%)	0 (0.0%)	79424 (83.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	20	0	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	20 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	309721	0	59110 (19.1%)	0 (0.0%)	250611 (80.9%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	95427	0	18958 (19.9%)	0 (0.0%)	76469 (80.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	106766	0	18018 (16.9%)	0 (0.0%)	88748 (83.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	29802	0	8401 (28.2%)	0 (0.0%)	21401 (71.8%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	216465	0	72703 (33.6%)	0 (0.0%)	143762 (66.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	3147	0	293 (9.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2854 (90.7%)	0 (0.0%)

Facility UID	All Patient #	Paxlovid Prescriptions	COVID Patients	COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid	Non-COVID Patients	Non-COVID Patients Prescribed Paxlovid
*** Masked ***	114371	0	18765 (16.4%)	0 (0.0%)	95606 (83.6%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	13690	0	76 (0.6%)	0 (0.0%)	13614 (99.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	45248	0	7827 (17.3%)	0 (0.0%)	37421 (82.7%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	49556	0	8628 (17.4%)	0 (0.0%)	40928 (82.6%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	155039	0	32360 (20.9%)	0 (0.0%)	122679 (79.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	175095	0	42696 (24.4%)	0 (0.0%)	132399 (75.6%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	129178	0	12759 (9.9%)	0 (0.0%)	116419 (90.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	172321	0	30906 (17.9%)	0 (0.0%)	141415 (82.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	93540	0	15663 (16.7%)	0 (0.0%)	77877 (83.3%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	66911	0	11045 (16.5%)	0 (0.0%)	55866 (83.5%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	114140	0	19323 (16.9%)	0 (0.0%)	94817 (83.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	44561	0	8455 (19.0%)	0 (0.0%)	36106 (81.0%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	31689	0	6497 (20.5%)	0 (0.0%)	25192 (79.5%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	39742	0	9782 (24.6%)	0 (0.0%)	29960 (75.4%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	534426	0	521193 (97.5%)	0 (0.0%)	13233 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	47972	0	10489 (21.9%)	0 (0.0%)	37483 (78.1%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	28687	0	2645 (9.2%)	0 (0.0%)	26042 (90.8%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	49574	0	1970 (4.0%)	0 (0.0%)	47604 (96.0%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	8892	0	1456 (16.4%)	0 (0.0%)	7436 (83.6%)	0 (0.0%)
*** Masked ***	100088	0	6806 (6.8%)	0 (0.0%)	93282 (93.2%)	0 (0.0%)

Observations: Paxlovid prescriptions by different health care facilities were tabulated for COVID and Non-COVID patients. From the 57 health care facilities, 40% (23) provided at least one

paxlovid prescription and 60% (34) had no Paxlovid prescriptions. Out of the 6,076,060 total patients from all facilities, only 16,712 patients were prescribed Paxlovid. The sample of patients who received Paxlovid included mostly COVID patients, with a small sample of Non-COVID patients (i.e., no COVID test or diagnosis) receiving paxlovid. Only 25.5% (1,550,264) of the total sample were COVID patients, and approximately 1% (15,291) of those patients received Paxlovid. Of the Non-COVID patients, 0.03% (1,421) of those patients had Paxlovid prescriptions.

Table 2. Characteristics of Patients receiving Paxlovid

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	Started 12/1/21-3/31/22 # (%)	Started 4/1/22-5/30/22 # (%)
Mean age	54.87	55.4	54.77
Median (IQR) Age	56.0 (42.0-68.0)	57.0 (42.0-69.0)	56.0 (42.0-68.0)
Age groups			
<1	<20	<20	<20
1-4	122 (0.7%)	20 (0.7%)	102 (0.7%)
10-15	269 (1.6%)	46 (1.7%)	223 (1.6%)
16-20	2113 (12.6%)	367 (13.2%)	1746 (12.5%)
21-35	2625 (15.7%)	396 (14.3%)	2229 (16.0%)
36-45	2960 (17.7%)	454 (16.3%)	2506 (18.0%)
46-55	3489 (20.9%)	594 (21.4%)	2895 (20.8%)
56-65	5133 (30.7%)	900 (32.4%)	4233 (30.4%)
66+	<20	<20	<20
Sex			
Male	6536 (39.1%)	1118 (40.3%)	5418 (38.9%)
Female	10169 (60.9%)	1659 (59.7%)	8510 (61.1%)
Other/Missing/Unknown	<20	<20	<20
Race ethnicity			
Non-Hispanic white	12315 (73.7%)	2010 (72.4%)	10305 (74.0%)
Non-Hispanic black	1432 (8.6%)	283 (10.2%)	1149 (8.2%)
Hispanic	1288 (7.7%)	207 (7.5%)	1081 (7.8%)
Non-Hispanic Asian	701 (4.2%)	77 (2.8%)	624 (4.5%)
Non-Hispanic other	171 (1.0%)	56 (2.0%)	115 (0.8%)
Missing/Unknown	805 (4.8%)	144 (5.2%)	661 (4.7%)
Any vaccination documented			

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	Started 12/1/21-3/31/22 # (%)	Started 4/1/22-5/30/22 # (%)
At least one vaccine before COVID	9930 (59.4%)	1320 (47.5%)	8610 (61.8%)
At least one vaccine post COVID	42 (0.3%)	32 (1.2%)	<20
COVID severity			
Hospitalized	426 (2.5%)	130 (4.7%)	296 (2.1%)
Ventilator	<20	<20	<20
Mean COVID Hospitalization length of stay	3.29	4.08	2.94
Median (IQR) COVID Hospitalization length of stay	1.0 (1.0-3.0)	1.0 (1.0-4.0)	1.0 (1.0-2.0)
Paxlovid Characteristics			
Mean time from index to Paxlovid start date (Pax before COVID)	2.06	1.46	2.18
Median (IQR) time from index to Paxlovid start date in days (pax before covid)	0.0 (0.0-1.0)	0.0 (0.0-1.0)	1.0 (1.0-2.0)
Mean time from index to Paxlovid start date (Pax after COVID)	7.56	18.59	4.8
Median (IQR) time from index to Paxlovid start date in days (pax after covid)	3.0 (1.0-8.0)	5.0 (1.0-24.0)	2.0 (1.0-7.0)
Start more than 30 days before infection date (pax before covid)	223 (1.3%)	27 (1.0%)	196 (1.4%)
Start within 30 days of infection date (pax before covid)	394 (2.4%)	63 (2.3%)	331 (2.4%)
Start within 30 days of infection date (pax after covid)	14652 (87.7%)	2451 (88.3%)	12201 (87.6%)
Start more than 30 days of infection date (pax after covid)	22 (0.1%)	20 (0.7%)	<20
No documentation of COVID	1421 (8.5%)	216 (7.8%)	1205 (8.6%)
Total Count	16712	2777	13935

Observations: In this analysis, we describe characteristics of patients receiving Paxlovid in three columns of Table 2: a) overall, b) those who received Paxlovid during 12/1/2021-3/31/2022, and c) those who received Paxlovid during 4/1/2022-5/30/2022. The majority of Paxlovid patients occurred during the 4/1/2022-5/30/2022 period. Those patients defined as receiving Paxlovid were more likely to be the older age groups of 56-65 and 65+, more likely to be White non-Hispanic, and more likely to be female. Approximately 87.7% of the patients started Paxlovid

within 30 days after their COVID infection date. Only a small proportion of patients in this sample were hospitalized (2.5%) or had no documentation of COVID (8.5%).

Discussion

Only 40% of N3C sites report providing at least one paxlovid prescription to patients during our study period. We find that 83% of paxlovid prescriptions recorded in N3C data occurred in the last two months of our study period. The average time to receive paxlovid reduced from 18 days to less than 5 days and the median time reduced from 5 days to 2 days. We find a steady increase in the number of prescriptions over time as well. Future releases of N3C data will likely lead to a larger sample for analyzing PASC in patients that have received paxlovid. Given that paxlovid is targeted to individuals with at least one risk factor for severe covid, the patients receiving paxlovid are older (mean age 55 years old) adults. Close to 60% of patients who received paxlovid had at least one vaccine prior to their covid index. Individuals receiving paxlovid in N3C have a very low prevalence of hospitalization (2.5%). For patients who are hospitalized, they have an average length of stay of 3 days (median 1 day).

Limitations

We exclude patients that had a COVID index prior to the study period and omit 1,077 patients from the study. Future work can analyze these patients to understand indications for their receipt of paxlovid. Because we use the earliest COVID positive incidence as the index date, reinfections are not included in analysis. A rise in at-home testing may also decrease the number of new index dates, allowing patients to have a Paxlovid record without an index date.